

Polarographic Determination of Bismuth (III) with Tetraethylenepentamine

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Bismuth gives a well defined, diffusion controlled reduction wave in 0.4M tetraethylenepentamine with half wave potential -0.657 V vs. SCE, which is used for determination.

TETRAETHYLENEPENTAMINE (abbreviated as tetren) has already been reported for the chelatometric, potentiometric^{1,2} and spectrophotometric³ determination of many metal ions. Only few waves for bismuth have been reported in basic media⁴⁻⁷ but these are not well defined. In the present communication, a polarographic method has been developed for the determination of bismuth using tetren as base electrolyte.

Experimental

Apparatus :

All polarograms were recorded with a Manual Adept polarograph at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$ and dissolved oxygen was removed by passing nitrogen for about five minutes. Saturated calomel electrode was used as reference electrode connected to the cell through saturated KCl-agar bridge. The value of m and t were 1.85 mg/sec. and 3.20 sec. respectively in distilled water and open circuit. pH measurements were made with a Philips pH meter.

Effect of tetren concentration and of pH :

The effect of tetren concentration was studied by taking different concentrations of tetren. It was found that the half wave potential shifted to more negative potentials with the increase in tetren concentration, but not appreciably as indicated in Table 1. The reduction wave remained well defined in 0.1M to 0.8M tetren range of concentration.

The wave is well defined in the pH 8.5 to 11.0 range, however the half wave potential shifted to lesser negative potentials with the decrease in pH.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF TETREN CONCENTRATION ON $E_{1/2}$ OF BISMUTH

Bi = 1.6 mM, S = 1/20

S.No.	Tetren concentration	$E_{1/2}$ vs. S.C.E.
1.	0.1 M	-0.627
2.	0.2 M	-0.640
3.	0.4 M	-0.657
4.	0.6 M	-0.662
5.	0.8 M	-0.667

Effect of bismuth concentration :

A series of polarograms was recorded by taking different concentrations of bismuth ion in 0.4M tetren. When the diffusion current was plotted against bismuth concentration, a straight line was obtained. (Table 2).

TABLE 2—RELATION BETWEEN DIFFUSION CURRENT AND BISMUTH CONCENTRATION

Tetren = 0.4M, S = 1/20.

S.No.	Concentration of Bi* (ml)	Diffusion current (arbitrary units)
1.	0.4	3.5
2.	0.8	7.0
3.	1.2	10.5
4.	1.6	14.0
5.	2.0	17.5
6.	2.4	21.0
7.	2.8	25.0

* 1 ml of Bi solution added \equiv 0.8 mM of Bismuth concentration

Results and Discussion

The effect of mercury column height on the diffusion current was also studied. The linear plot of i_d vs. \sqrt{h} indicated the diffusion controlled nature of the reduction, which was already suggested by the linear plot of diffusion current vs. bismuth concentration. The plot of $\log(i/i_d - i)$ vs. E also came out to be a straight line and the slope of this plot and the value of $E_{3/4} - E_{1/4}$ which is 62 mV, since do not agree with the theoretical values, indicated the irreversibility of the reduction wave. Due to this irreversibility no deduction can be made about the nature of the complex formed during reduction. Comparing the diffusion current with known reduction wave shows the three electron change i.e.,

since the plot of diffusion current vs. bismuth concentration is linear and the wave is well defined ($E_{1/2} = -0.657$ V in 0.4 tetren), this reduction can be used for the quantitative determination of Bi.

Procedure of the Bismuth determination :

A calibration graph was prepared by taking some known concentration of bismuth (0.3 to 2.5 mM) in 0.4M tetren and then the polarograms were recorded of some sample solution with unknown concentration of Bi under identical conditions and the values of the diffusion current were referred to the calibration graph for the determination. The results of some sample solution analyses are given in Table 3.

TABLE 3—DETERMINATION OF BISMUTH ION CONCENTRATION

Tetren = 0.4M, S = 1/20

Sample No.	Concentration (mM)	
	Taken	Found
1.	0.650	0.650
2.	0.900	0.895
3.	1.200	1.205
4.	1.800	1.800
5.	2.220	2.225

Interferences

Metal ions like Fe, Sb, Sn, Th and Mn get precipitated and do not influence the diffusion current due to bismuth, so cause no interference. Metal ions as Cd, Ni, Zn, In, Ag undergo reduction at different potentials, so do not interfere and so the determination of Bi can be carried out in the presence of these metal ions. Tl, Cu and Co interfere in this method. The advantages of this base electrolyte is that a single well defined wave is obtained and there is no need of any maximum suppressor or auxiliary electrolyte.

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